

MODELLING EDGE EFFECTS ON COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF FIBRE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Compressive failure of engineering fibre composites is generally governed by plastic microbuckling, initiated at waviness defects [1]. Existing models of initiation have tended to consider idealised defects while recent work has shown that waviness can be randomly distributed, characterized by both the amplitude of the misalignment and the typical size of features [2]. Liu et al [3] have modelled a random distribution of waviness, in particular investigating the effect of fibre bending stiffness on the strength and critical defect characteristics. However, for the millimetre-scale defects sizes relevant to realistic waviness [2], fibre bending does not play a major role. A rebar modelling approach, which does not include fibre bending, was found to give an accurate prediction of the initiation event and peak load, even though it is not able to model the geometry of the ensuing microbuckle [4].

The effect of the reduced constraint at a free edge has been predicted to reduce the compressive strength at a critical (idealised) waviness feature [4-6] but it is not clear what effect edges would have with random waviness, where the critical feature may not be near the edge. Similar issues arise when considering size effects, which may lead to a decreased strength with increasing specimen size [7]. How would the increase in both the edge length and the volume of the specimen affect the strength as the specimen size increases? A finite element (FE) analysis is used in this paper to explore these issues, using a stochastic model of the waviness distribution to capture the statistics of compressive strength. Results with an idealised model of waviness are first presented to help interpret these results.

2 Finite element methodology

A two-dimensional (2D) Abaqus implicit FE model [8] is developed, following the general approach of [4], but with the implementation details significantly modified to improve the efficiency and accuracy.

2.1 Fibre orientation

2.1.1 Idealised waviness

This section follows closely the work described in [4], but uses a new more accurate FE methodology and an extended range of geometries. Three idealised waviness defect shapes within a square specimen of side length L are used to explore the effect of patch size and position: (i) square with a side length λ , (ii) rectangular with length (in the fibre direction) $\lambda = 0.1L$ and width ω (transverse to the fibres) either equal to $0.3L$ or L (in the later case the waviness misalignment angle falls to zero at the edges) and (iii) an 'infinite band' of misalignment of length $\lambda = 0.1L$ which does not vary in fibre orientation across the width. The square defect and rectangular defect spanning the full width of the specimen are illustrated in Fig. 1. The peak fibre misalignment angle is ϕ_m and the distribution of waviness ϕ within the patch has a sinusoidal variation, following [4],

$$\phi(x, y) = \phi_m \cos\left(\frac{x\pi}{\lambda}\right) \cos\left(\frac{y\pi}{\omega}\right) \quad (1)$$

where x and y are co-ordinates in the fibre and transverse direction, respectively, with origin at the centre of the waviness patch. The same variation of waviness in the fibre direction is used with the infinite band model.

In the above cases the defect is located at the middle of the specimen. Calculations are also done with a square patch with side length $\lambda = 0.1L$, with the centre of the patch midway between the two loaded edges but offset towards one of the free edges by a distance y' . For all these idealised geometries the rebar orientation defining the fibre direction is implemented using an 'orient' subroutine, defining the orientation of rebar elements in the model.

2.1.2 Random waviness

A random distribution of fibre misalignment with a given average feature length λ and standard

deviation in orientation ϕ_m is generated by applying smoothing to a finer random grid of waviness distributions. The waviness distribution is faded out at the loading ends to avoid end effects. A typical variation of waviness is given in Fig. 2. At least 40 realisations are used to capture the random nature of the waviness.

As well as the case illustrated in Fig. 2, where waviness defects persist to the free edges, an alternative arrangement was used with the waviness defect amplitude faded to zero towards the free edges (in a similar way as for the loaded edges), over a region at the edges of width equal to either 0.25λ or λ . This aims to capture the case where tooling or adjacent plies prevent formation of severe waviness defects right at the free edge of the specimen. For these random waviness orientations, the orientation of each rebar element was directly specified, using a Matlab routine to generate an appropriate Abaqus input data file.

2.2 Material model

For both idealised and random waviness models the material model is representative of a unidirectional CFRP laminate, following the approach in [4]. A layer of solid elements is used to capture the shear response, with von Mises perfectly-plastic behaviour giving a composite shear yield stress τ_y . The effect of unidirectional fibre reinforcement is included using elastic rebar elements contained within a membrane whose nodes are attached to corresponding nodes of the solid elements. Material properties for both components and for the resulting composite are detailed in Table 1, replicating properties in [4]. The shear modulus G of the resulting composite is 4.3 GPa.

2.3 Element and mesh details

For the idealised model, three-dimensional reduced integration elements (C3D8R) are used for the solid layer representing the shear response. The problem is rendered 2D by matching in-plane nodal displacements on opposing faces of the model. Out-of-plane constraints are imposed to give a generalised plane strain condition, with the opposing planes remaining flat and parallel, but with uniform out-of-plane strain allowed. The effect of relaxing this constraint to give plane-stress conditions was explored, and found to give a reduction of 5% in the failure load, for the idealised geometry with a central square defect with $\phi_m = 5^\circ$ and side length $\lambda = 0.1L$.

For the random waviness model, 2D plane strain elements (CPE4) are used for the solid layer representing the shear response.

For both the idealised and random waviness models rebar reinforcement is contained within a dummy membrane layer (element type M3D4R) whose nodes are attached to corresponding nodes on the solid layer. This membrane has a stiffness much less than the solid or rebar components.

The idealised geometry has a graded mesh, with smaller elements covering the waviness defect. A typical mesh for the case of $\lambda = 0.1L$ is illustrated in Fig. 3. A region of $3\lambda \times 3\lambda$ containing a square defect of size $\lambda \times \lambda$ has a fine mesh whilst the mesh is graded outside this critical region.

A mesh refinement study was undertaken for both the idealised and random geometries to establish the required mesh density. The results for the square idealised geometry are shown in Fig. 4, for the typical case of $\phi_m = 3^\circ$ and $\lambda = 0.1L$. The failure load, normalised by the shear yield strength of the composite, is plotted as a function of the ratio of the element length Δ in the fine mesh region around the defect to the defect length λ . In these calculations the mesh size in the graded region is scaled with the mesh size in the central region. There is some sensitivity to element size but, for the chosen mesh density with $\Delta/\lambda = 0.04$, the error associated with the finite mesh size is less than 1%, estimating the 'true' value by extrapolating results to zero Δ . For different geometries the mesh density in the critical region containing the defect was maintained at the chosen value of $\Delta/\lambda = 0.04$.

The random waviness model has a uniform mesh size throughout the model. A similar mesh sensitivity study was undertaken for this model and an appropriate mesh density was selected with the square element length equal to the smaller of $\lambda/20$ and $L/200$, see [9] for details.

2.4 Loading and failure response

Displacement loading is applied to the ends of the specimen. Under these conditions microbuckling failure is an unstable phenomenon. Figure 5 shows the collapse response for a typical idealised geometry, plotting the maximum shear strain in the composite (at the critical element which is in the centre of the waviness patch) as a function of mean applied stress. Figure 5 shows that the FE analysis for the standard model terminates when the rate of change of remote applied stress with the change in peak element strain tends to zero, confirming that a peak load has been reached.

Figure 5 includes insets showing the distribution of the shear strain around the waviness defect at a load

well before failure and at maximum load. The spatial scale is the same for these two insets, but the contour scaling has been varied to suit the maximum shear strain. The contour plots show how the shear strains localise to a single line of elements in the centre of the waviness defect.

Figure 5 shows that the behaviour up to maximum load is controlled by the response of a patch of waviness around the ensuing localisation, so that the maximum load is not dependent on the mesh size, as long as the critical defect is modelled with a sufficiently fine mesh.

The collapse response after peak load with the standard model is not modelled since the deformation collapses to a single line of elements. In other studies where fibre bending tends to stabilise the localisation event, the post-collapse response has been determined using a curve tracking (Riks) algorithm [e.g. 3], showing that once localisation has initiated failure is unstable. A model using the same conditions as plotted in Fig. 5, but taking just the inner $3\lambda \times 3\lambda$ region, was modified to investigate this effect. Linear beam elements were included within the model to give a small bending resistance but negligible change in other elastic properties. The collapse response for this model with bending resistance is included on Fig. 5. The bending resistance stabilises the localisation (with use of a Riks algorithm), giving a peak in the load and subsequent growth of the ensuing microbuckle. The response up to peak load is similar to that of the standard model, with slight differences associated with the reduction in size of the model with bending and the inclusion of the bending resistance itself.

The failure location is determined for the random waviness model by identifying the element with the largest shear strain at the maximum load, which invariably corresponded to an element where the rate of change of remote stress with shear strain tended to zero.

2.5 Effect of off-axis plies

The above approach is modified to consider the effect of the constraint of adjacent off-axis plies on failure in a central unidirectional ply. The geometry is illustrated in Fig. 6. The central square gauge section of side-length L contains random waviness, with the material properties detailed in section 2.2. Adjacent plies, of width L , have the stiffness and strength properties reduced from the values in Table 1 by a knock-down factor.

3 Results

3.1 Idealised waviness

Figure 7 shows the effect of the size and shape of the idealised patch on the strength, normalised by the composite shear yield strength. The strength depends on fibre misalignment angle as expected [1]. For a central idealised square patch of waviness the strength is insensitive to the ratio λ/L of the side-length of the waviness patch to the specimen width for $\lambda/L < 0.1$. This result mirrors the insensitivity to free edge effects, for sufficiently large specimens compared with the defect size, both of the stress concentration at a circular hole and of the stress intensity factor at a central crack [10].

The "infinite band" calculation is in excellent agreement at larger misalignment angles with the Budiansky kink band prediction [11], but gives a lower strength at smaller peak misalignment angles. Here the axial stress in the matrix contributes significantly to the von Mises stress, an effect not considered in the Budiansky analysis.

The results of Fig. 7 differ from those in [4], Fig. 11. It appears that inaccuracies associated with an insufficiently fine mesh have been introduced for the smallest features used in [4], Fig. 11, giving rise to a significant over-prediction of the strength and leading to the erroneous conclusion that strength increases significantly for very small features. Additional calculations with the long thin features modelled in [4] have confirmed this conclusion in a further direct comparison.

Moving the position y' of the centre of the waviness defect towards the free edge results in a significant drop in strength, see Fig. 8, in which strengths are normalised by the strength with a central defect. As the centre of the patch nears the free edge ($y'/L = 0$) part of the defect 'falls off the edge', reducing the defect size and giving the slight rise in strength observed at the very edge. These results agree with predictions in [4].

3.2 Random waviness

Figure 9 shows the distribution of failure locations across the width of the specimen, for a ratio λ/L of the defect size to the specimen width equal to 0.1, taking the results of 80 realisations with $\phi_m = 1.5^\circ$. Failures are concentrated near the free edges for the case with defects persisting to the edge, Fig. 9(a). This is expected given the reduction in strength seen for the idealised waviness with defects near the free edge, see Fig. 8. Nevertheless, in a significant proportion of cases failure occurs away from the

edges. The random distribution of waviness means that sometimes a more severe feature away from the edges is more critical than milder features near the edge. Where defects are eliminated from the free edge, failure occurs uniformly across the centre of the specimen, see Fig. 9(b).

Figure 10 shows the effect of the ratio L/λ of the specimen width to the defect size on the ratio σ_c/τ_y of the compressive strength to the composite shear yield stress. Results are a mean of 40 realisations. The large number of realisations used ensures that the error in the mean, estimated from the standard deviation of strengths, is roughly equal to the size of the markers in the figure. Eliminating defects at the free edges significantly increases the predicted strength, both with only a relatively narrow defect-free strip of width 0.25λ and a wider strip of width λ . Note that predictions are not included for the smallest value of L/λ with waviness eliminated over the edge region of width λ , as most of the sample would be affected in that case.

There is a significant decrease in the predicted strength with increasing size. This is because the chance of including larger defects in the model increases with increasing size. Where defects are precluded at the edges, so that the body of the specimen contains the critical defect, this decrease in strength with increasing size is more severe. This difference is because the area of regions near the edges scales with the length L while the total area scales with L^2 .

3.3 Effect of adjacent plies

Figure 11 shows the effect of the edge constraint of an adjacent ply on the failure strain. Values plotted are the mean of 20 values. Because the same set of waviness realisations was used for each point plotted, a smaller number of calculations is sufficient to identify the differences in strength reliably. Results with no adjacent ply (i.e. only a free edge) are included, identified by a knock-down factor on material properties of zero, while the other limit with material properties in the adjacent plies equal to that of the central ply (although without any waviness in the outside plies) corresponds to a knockdown factor on properties of one. Two lines are given, where the knockdown factor is applied to both stiffness and strength, and where only the stiffness is adjusted. This latter case could be considered more relevant to off-axis plies, since ply shear failure is relatively unaffected by the fibre orientation, while the axial stiffness is considerably changed. There is a significant increase in failure

strain associated with the constraint of the adjacent ply, with the effect varying smoothly between the two extreme constraint conditions. There is minimal difference between the cases where only elastic or both elastic and plastic properties are changed. A knockdown factor of 0.25, corresponding loosely to adjacent $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, gives an increase in failure strain of 12% compared with the free edge condition, while being 14% lower than the case of an adjacent 0° ply.

4 Summary

The effect of edges on compressive failure of fibre composites has been explored using finite element analysis. For an idealised geometry with a square or rectangular waviness defect, the usual reduction of strength with increasing fibre misalignment has been observed. For sufficiently small defects, with the ratio λ/L of defect size to specimen size less than 0.1, the strength is insensitive to the defect size. The strength drops significantly for defects close to the free edge.

Results for specimens with a random distribution of waviness predict a concentration of failures at the edge of the specimen, reflecting the observed reduction in strength for idealised waviness near the edge. The predicted mean strength falls with an increasing ratio L/λ of specimen size to defect size. Where waviness is excluded from near the free edges, a situation which might arise due to manufacturing effects, failure is uniformly distributed through the specimen and the strength of the composite significantly increases.

The effect of the constraint of adjacent off-axis plies is considered by introducing a knock-down in strength or stiffness of material abutting a central 0° ply. The introduction of off-axis plies lead to a significant increase in the predicted failure strain, with material properties roughly corresponding to adjacent $\pm 45^\circ$ plies giving an increase in failure strain of 12% compared with the free edge condition.

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	Solid layer	Rebar layer	Resulting composite
E_1 (GPa)	11.2	230	146
$E_2 = E_3$ (GPa)	11.2	n/a	11.2
τ_y (MPa)	64.7	n/a	64.7
ν_{12}	0.3	0.3	0.3
Fibre volume fraction ν_f	n/a	0.588	n/a

Table 1: Material properties.

Fig. 1. Geometry of idealised waviness (after [4]).

Fig 2. Contours of fibre orientation ϕ , for random waviness with characteristic defect size $\lambda = 0.1L$.

Fig. 3. Typical mesh used for the idealised waviness model (square defect, $\lambda = 0.1L$).

Fig. 4. Mesh refinement study for an idealised square-defect waviness geometry ($\phi_m = 3^\circ$, $\lambda = 0.1L$).

Fig. 5. Collapse response showing the change in peak shear strain with remote mean applied stress for an idealised square-defect waviness geometry, $\phi_m = 3^\circ$, $\lambda = 0.1L$. The insets show the composite shear strain around the waviness defect superimposed on a mesh with $\times 10$ displacement amplification.

Fig. 6. Model to investigate the effect of off-axis plies.

Fig 7. Effect of peak misalignment angle ϕ_m and patch geometry on strength.

Fig 8. Effect of the position y/L of the centre of a square defect on the strength, normalised by the strength for a central defect ($\phi_m = 3^\circ$, $\lambda = 0.1L$).

Fig 9. Distance y/L from the free edge of the failure location: (a) no fade-out of waviness at free edge, (b) waviness faded over edge region of width $\lambda = 0.1L$ (random waviness, $\phi_m = 1.5^\circ$, $\lambda = 0.1L$).

Fig 10. Effect on strength of ratio L/λ of width of specimen to size of random defect ($\phi_m = 1.5^\circ$).

Fig 11. Effect of the constraint of adjacent plies on the failure strain in a central 0° ply containing random waviness with $\phi_m = 1.5^\circ$, $\lambda = 0.1L$.